

iSpot

Case Studies

Demonstrating Cos4Cloud success stories
and best practice examples

Cos4Cloud case studies description

This case study is an output from the Cos4Cloud project which demonstrates evidence-based knowledge of project approaches and their impact. It is part of a collection in the [Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence Hub](#) and shared as part of the legacy and lessons learned from the project. These include a range of stories and experiences collated from activity generated throughout the lifetime of the project such as blogs and articles, as well as user-friendly presentations that showcase selected best practices.

Case study title

Evaluating the learning potential of citizen observatories: a case study of iSpotnature.org: an online learning community for nature lovers

Case study contributing partner and Citizen Observatory lead

Cos4Cloud Coordinator

What is the case study about?

This Case study explores the citizen science learning potential of citizen observatories by demonstrating examples of iSpot activity, that highlight the learning potential from online activities focused on collecting and sharing biodiversity data. iSpot is a citizen science platform (citizen observatory) for biodiversity developed and operated by The Open University (OU). It is aimed at helping anyone share wildlife observations, identify, explore and learn about nature.

iSpot is one of the nine citizen observatories involved in the Cos4Cloud project. Cos4Cloud is developing thirteen services boosting citizen science technological services to help increase and improve the quantity and quality of observations.

CHALLENGE: WHAT DID THIS SEEK TO DO / SOLVE?

The scale and range of online citizen science projects and initiatives focused on biodiversity has evolved, particularly over the past 10 - 20 years. Alongside this interest and increasing public participation, is growing recognition of its role contributing to learning. **How can these types of user experiences be explored from the context of learning in a citizen observatory and demonstrated as learner / learning journeys?**

The concept of a learning / learner journey applies to different educational settings and can be defined simply as a way to describe one's own experience, referring "to how people move between different types (or periods) of learning" (Thomson, 2021). User journeys can evolve reflecting spaces that stage the experience; interaction time which also influences the activity; how participants engage and the role of environment facilitating the experience (Benford, 2009)

As part of Cos4Cloud a review was conducted exploring citizen science participant learning journeys by analysing iSpot user experiences, from the context of a range of learning approaches, as an exemplar for other citizen observatories. The evaluation approach was developed using insight from a five-step thematic method: explore, identify, contribute, personalise and recognition (learning) (Ansine et al, 2017).

AUDIENCE REACH AND METHODS OF ENGAGEMENT

iSpot was launched by the OU in 2009 and uses the challenge of identifying nature to engage people, as citizen scientists, encouraging learning about biodiversity while building species identification skills. iSpot is based in the UK but is global: anyone can

browse the platform and take a look at the latest spots. Users are encouraged to learn while sharing their interest with a friendly community by registering, uploading photos and adding observations, joining in discussions, supporting others and getting help identifying what they have seen. iSpot aims to:

- Lower barriers to ID – build ID skills
- Make nature accessible / open to all
- A new generation of naturalists
- Contribute to biological data recording

The website incorporates a range of features and tools that support and facilitate learning, these include: global, national species dictionaries, integrated tools (i.e. quizzes and projects), links to resources and courses directly contributing to informal & formal learning.

iSpot: your place to share nature: a step by step approach

Explore: browse observations; register / sign in to upload your own, other users can help to identify what you have seen.

Record: add as much information as you can; if you think you know the species name you can say so.

Identify: build your reputation in species ID and see the scores of those who have agreed with your identification.

Learn: Test your knowledge take quizzes, use ID keys and tools.

iSpot supports a global online community of over 80,000 registered users and reaches a wider audience through engagement activities including media, radio & TV (OU/BBC co-productions), social media, events & activities with schools, community groups etc; connections and collaborations with recording schemes and societies and other organisations.

This case study summarises an evaluation of the science learning potential of citizen science observatories, through iSpot, defining 'learning journeys through the user experiences of this online community. The OU has extended engagement, teaching and learning about the natural world beyond the parameters of the laboratory or lecture hall through citizen science i.e. iSpot.

BENEFITS AND OR OUTCOMES

Summary: iSpot community learning experiences

Evaluation themes	Learning approaches	iSpotnature.org user community experience / activity	iSpot review and analysis (examples)
Explore	Social Learning	A free online platform - anyone can browse iSpot: analytics data shows an average of 9 pages viewed per session with an average session duration of 8 – 10 minutes.	Participant learner engagement from purposive browsing. i.e. iSpot's 'browse observation' search page was the second highest page viewed. (Ansine, et al, 2017) p87.
Identify	Participatory learning	Registered participants can post observations and photos; gather content, share comments and in doing so give and receive help with species identification.	iSpot is described as having a participatory learning approach where an active participant the learner engages in activity, developing their interest and passion" (Clow et al, 2011).
Contribute	Experiential learning	iSpot integrates participant rewards and motivation through a bespoke reputation system.	Registered participants gain scores for each of the species groups represented. iSpot gives points / scores for activity and this is a key feature behind how the site works (Silvertown, et al. 2015).
Personalise	Personalised learning	iSpot has tools and features that encourage and facilitate personalisation to meet the participants' interest and pace i.e. iSpot projects.	iSpot's design is described as one which gives participants control over the learning process (Scanlon et al. 2014) through technology with integrated tools and features (Woods et al. 2016). Over 3,000 projects were added in the first two years the feature was added (2014 – 2016) highlighting personalised interest based on selected sites, regions, habitat, species and / or time frames (Ansine et al. 2017).
Recognition	Active learning	iSpot has integrated and bespoke learning assessment tools i.e. iSpot quizzes; and associated courses. iSpot Quiz data / structured courses projects data	iSpot quizzes were added in 2013 as an assessment tool to support / provide evidence of learning, within the first year of development quizzes were done by approximately 50 participants per week (Scanlon et al. 2013). iSpot is also integrated into OU formal and informal courses i.e. Citizen science and global biodiversity.

IMPACT

This case study summarises examples of learning reviewed within the context of established learning approaches applied to iSpot user activity. Analysis of user experience, so far, suggests that citizen science learner journeys can occur individually as well as part of group experiences. This includes participation through the use of tools and features i.e. [iSpot projects](#); as well as through the identification support provided from the integration of technological services i.e. Cos4Cloud services [FASTCAT-Cloud](#) and the [PI@ntNet API](#).

iSpot's citizen science user learner / learning journeys can be described as experiences that occur which are controlled by the participant; each unique in its own way based on levels of expertise / pre-existing knowledge and the amount of time spent involved. They can be on single or multiple topics which stop, start, continue based on the motivation and / or interest influencing engagement and experience.

Influenced by the results of this review, conducted as part of Cos4Cloud, iSpot's engagement and learning model was reviewed, revised and updated to better demonstrate, outline and introduce the iSpot user experience as a defined user learning journey across four updated themes: [Explore!](#) [Record!](#) [Collaborate!](#) [Learn!](#)

Explore: Browse the thousands of observations spotted so far

Anyone can see what's on the site, from the [homepage](#), and click on the photos for the latest sightings. Select a *Community* i.e. UK & Ireland, Global etc. Under the carousels of images, click the *Filter by Group* buttons to view more of the latest posts in the species group that may interest you. Go to *Explore Community* and open the [Species browser](#) to *explore* more.

Record: Submit your observation, try to identify it and the community will help

To *record* (i.e. submit observations) registration and logging in is required. Click on the [Sign up to iSpot](#) button, provide a username, email address, and password. Check email for an iSpot confirmation message. Get photos of wildlife, comments and / or queries ready to record and *add an observation!* Add all the information you can and try to identify it; ask the community, others can help. For assistance with what to spot, where to see and how to identify it check out the [Species Browser](#). When logged in, do check the 'Your iSpot' user profile area and go to the 'Activity and Changes Trackers' to see if anyone has identified or commented on observations or interacted with your comments. **Remember, you need to have registered and logged in to access these areas.**

Collaborate: Engage in discussions, help others identify and build your iSpot reputation

Once registered you become part of the iSpot community. *Collaborate* with others and *contribute* in a number of ways: add observations, assist others by commenting, agreeing or adding identifications (IDs) to their observations. Want to chat with others on a range of topics? Go to 'Explore Community' and select the [iSpot Forums](#). Visit 'Your iSpot' to see your profile, click on your username on the frontpage to find this. From here you can access the integrated [reputation system](#) which shows rewards as badges, providing a record of progress on an iSpot user journey! **Remember, you need to have registered and logged in to access these areas.**

Learn: Take quizzes, join online courses, use identification keys and create projects

Learning, and helping others to *learn*, while sharing nature is a core aim of iSpot. We want to help build biological species identification skills and there are a range of tools and resources to help you on your iSpot learning journey. Participate in citizen science activities (see our frontpage news stories for ideas and opportunities), develop and shape [projects](#) to *personalise* and filter your interests and experiences. Integrated [quizzes](#) and [ID Keys](#), at different levels, challenge and recognise knowledge. There are also various Open University courses, some of which are [free](#), and can help to enhance and support a more structured learning journey. Join others and learn with The Open University, check out [this free course](#) about citizen science and global biodiversity.

Evaluation, research and analysis is ongoing exploring and documenting iSpot user journeys seeking to better understand experiences of learning from the perspectives of iSpot participants themselves. This includes analysing user comments, other contributions on the platform and investigating motivations for participation. iSpot user comments, for example, are an important and rich source towards understanding

participant behaviour. As these and further findings are shared as best practice experiences, it is anticipated that this will help to foster new understanding of learning in citizen science facilitated by citizen observatories, through the practice of a citizen observatory with an online community focused on biodiversity.

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LINKS TO FURTHER SUPPORT

Interested in learning about biodiversity with iSpot?

- Are you a keen nature observer, recorder or citizen scientist?
- Would you like to have your wildlife identification skills and contributions recognised?
- Want to experience your own citizen science 'learning journey'?

Join the free OU course: [Citizen science and global biodiversity](#)

Complete the course and get an Open University Badge and Statement of Participation! Go to: www.open.ac.uk/citizen-science-and-global-biodiversity

Additional resources: [About the Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence Hub](#)

This Cos4Cloud case study shares a summary of iSpot (www.ispotnature.org) activity, that demonstrates learning through a citizen observatory. The Open University's (OU) is a project partner and the OU's iSpot is one of the COs involved in the Cos4Cloud project (<https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/>). **Title: Evaluating the learning potential of citizen observatories: a case study of iSpotnature.org: an online learning community for nature lovers.** Author: Janice Ansine, The Open University. It is one of the Case Studies in the Cos4Cloud Toolbox & Evidence Hub developed by the Open University in collaboration with project partners. Contact: cos4cloud-toolbox@open.ac.uk.

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